

Quanti Farm

THE TOOLKIT

quantifarm.eu

FACTSHEET #1

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WHAT IS THE QUANTIFARM TOOLKIT?

QuantiFarm has assessed the performance of various Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions (DATSs) implemented by commercial farms through 30 Test Cases across 20 countries, representing diverse biogeographical regions of the EU and seven agricultural sectors. The QuantiFarm Toolkit – an inclusive, web-based platform – offers users access to these evaluation results through a user-friendly dashboard. It presents real-world evidence on the benefits, limitations, and context-specific performance of DATSs, thereby supporting informed decision-making among farmers, advisors, policymakers, and other stakeholders in the agricultural sector.

KEY OBJECTIVES

Provide reliable, comparable assessments of DATSs

Support decision-making for selecting
and investing in DATSs

Enable users to estimate economic, social,
and environmental impacts

Strengthen collaboration between farmers,
advisors, technology providers, and policymakers

MAIN FEATURES

Recommendation Tool

The QuantiFarm Recommendation Tool helps farmers and advisers identify the most suitable Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions (DATSs) based on their specific farm characteristics, needs, and objectives. By combining data from real-life test cases with user inputs, the tool generates tailored recommendations indicating which technologies offer the highest potential value in terms of performance, cost-effectiveness, and sustainability impact. It supports evidence-based decision-making and reduces uncertainty when selecting new digital tools.

Cost & Benefit Calculators

The Cost & Benefit Calculators help farmers and advisers estimate the financial impact of adopting digital agriculture technologies Solutions (DATSs). Through dedicated modules for crop and livestock systems, users can explore data from both commercial technologies and QuantiFarm test cases. By entering basic information — such as farm size, number of units, years of use, yield, and costs — the tool generates key economic indicators including operational savings, potential revenue gains, Return on Investment (ROI), and Net Benefit. This provides users with a clear, realistic view of the economic feasibility and profitability of DATSs across their lifecycle.

Policy Monitoring Tool

The Policy Monitoring Tool provides policymakers with an interactive dashboard for analysing regional agricultural performance using data from QuantiFarm test cases and multiple European datasets. It visualises anonymised, aggregated information from parcels using and not using DATSs, combined with Earth Observation products and official statistics, to generate summary tables, charts, and regional comparisons. Through indicators grouped into thematic categories, the tool supports three core functions: tracking generalised sustainability indicators, assessing DATSs vs. non-DATSs performance, and benchmarking regions against established thresholds. This enables evidence-based policy evaluation and more informed decision-making at regional level.

Real Assessment Results

QuantiFarm evaluates the performance of Digital Agricultural Technology Solutions (DATSs) across 30 real-life Test Cases. More details on the assessment methodology are available [here](#). The evaluation results refer strictly to the specific context in which each assessment was conducted (e.g., parcel, year, crop type, and local conditions).

MAIN FEATURES

WHO IS IT FOR?

Farmers & Farmers' Organisations

for practical decisions on whether to adopt a DATSs

Researchers

to access harmonised evaluation methodologies

Advisors & Advisory Services

for structured advisory support

Technology Providers

to showcase validated performance

Policymakers & Paying Agencies

to design evidence-based support measures

BENEFITS

Helps farmers reduce uncertainty when investing in digital What tools

Improves transparency and comparability across DATSs

Supports sustainable agriculture with measurable indicators

Strengthens the European digital agriculture ecosystem

Facilitates policy alignment with Green Deal, Farm-to-Fork, and CAP objectives

Toolkit Access

The Quantifarm Toolkit is available online through the project's official platform and continuously updated based on user feedback and new test results.

Contact

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